

USING EFFECTIVE WAYS OF CONDUCTING MARKETING RESEARCH IN INTERNATIONAL COMPANIES.

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Bazarova Mamlakat Supievna.

Asian International University.

Senior Lecturer, Department of Economics.

Abstract.

In this article, the use of effective ways of conducting marketing research on the example of international companies, analysis methods, SWOT analysis, the results of marketing research conducted on the market of Uzbekistan on the example of the RoboClean vacuum cleaner of the international company AURA Group are studied theoretically and practically.

Keywords.

AURA Group, commercial business, Aura Roboclean, marketing research, SWOT analysis, RoboClean vacuum cleaner.

A company (Latin: compania) - is an association of legal entities and individuals, entrepreneurs, organized to carry out economic activities (production, trade, brokerage, finance, insurance, etc.).

The term "company" refers to associations, companies, economic societies, firms, corporations, i.e. enterprises with various foreign legal forms. The company will have the status of a legal entity. The company can operate according to the principles of partnership, corporation, and other principles of business activity.¹⁴⁷

AURA Group is a sales and service IT company that has been operating since 2009 and is steadily improving year after year in the field of commercial business automation. Specializes in retail automation projects as well as local automation of manufacturing plants.¹⁴⁸

AURA group of companies is a sales and service IT company that always helps to organize business work more effectively.

The company will help you at any time¹⁴⁹:

¹⁴⁷ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kompaniya>

¹⁴⁸ [https://www.retail.ru/rbc/company/gruppa_kompaniy_aura/#:~:text=ГК%20"АУРА"%20является%20торгово-,таже%20локальной%20автоматизации%20производственных%20предприятий.](https://www.retail.ru/rbc/company/gruppa_kompaniy_aura/#:~:text=ГК%20)

¹⁴⁹ <http://roboclean.uz>

Both the head office and production facilities of Aura GmbH are located in Weiterstadt near Frankfurt, Germany.

Based on the belief that direct communication is the best and most reliable means of advertising, we sell our products exclusively through direct sales. By focusing our company's responsibility on maintaining the well-being of our customers, we have won the trust of families in more than 35 countries around the world. This success has been achieved by making the opinion of the customers and the continuous development and quality control of product models a top priority for us.

Our products are manufactured according to the ISO9001 directive in production facilities with high-tech infrastructure and presented to the consumer in accordance with international standards under the management of the continuously improving Advanced Development and Quality Department, which is responsible for the health of the consumer. At the production facilities, along with production, without sacrificing

quality, as a result of our sensitivity to the outside world, CDP (Carbon Footprint Project) activities are carried out.

As part of our health and customer policy, which began in 1996 and continues to this day, Aura Roboclean products have reached millions of consumers across geographies, spreading from east to west and from north to south. Designed to be productive, quiet and a friend of the user, this product has been recognized as a frontrunner and won the Red Dot Design Award 2013, Good Design 2015, Iconic Awards 2016 and IF Design 2016.

The continuation of a healthy life is the dream of every individual, society and nation. This is possible only through protection and living in a clean environment. Aura Roboclean, on the other hand, is not a goal to achieve this goal, but only a means. We are happy to produce this product for the health of our customers.¹⁵⁰

Using the above information, we conducted marketing research among the population on the RoboClean vacuum cleaner, one of the main products of the AURA company, and conducted a SWOT analysis based on the company's indicators.

According to the results of the AURA company's RoboClean vacuum cleaner survey, women make up 66,7% of 100% of participants, and men make up the remaining 33,3%. As for the age of the participants, those between 20-25 years old show the highest 50% result. The smallest indicator is 8,3% among 30-35-year-olds. 100% of our participants are from Bukhara region.

Most of the survey participants are students by profession, making up 66,7%. Employees and unemployed in private enterprises and state enterprises show the same indicator, i.e. they make up 16,7%. Pensioners make up 8,3%. Currently, 23,1% of the users of vacuum cleaners under different brands are Bosch, Samsung, and LG users. Those who use our Roboclean brand vacuum cleaner in their daily life show the highest rate, i.e. 30,8%.

As for the choice of our participants, 53,8% of those who pay attention to the price and convenience, 30,8% of those who pay attention to the brand, 23,1% of those who pay attention to the service, and those who pay attention to the quality are the highest results, with 92,3%.

All our participants buy a vacuum cleaner based on the variety of functions, 30,8% rated roboclean vacuum cleaner service in their region as excellent, 20,8% rated it moderately, 10% rated it poorly, and 31,6% did not use it yet. If we come to the opinion of the participants on how to eliminate the shortcomings, we can see that there were many opinions.

For example, we can see that due to the shortness of the cord, we have been asked to change to an electric vacuum cleaner, to strengthen it to eliminate noise, and to extend the cord. We are sure that the reason why the non-users have not yet taken it for their daily life is the high price and the fact that they are not yet aware of this technique.

Based on the above information, we came to the following conclusion and carried out a SWOT analysis of the company's activity.

Components of SWOT Analysis¹⁵¹

Every SWOT analysis will include the following four categories. Though the elements and discoveries within these categories will vary from company to company, a SWOT analysis is not complete without each of these elements:

Strengths

Strengths describe what an organization excels at and what separates it from the competition: a strong brand, loyal customer base, a strong balance sheet, unique technology, and so on. For example, a hedge fund may have developed a proprietary trading strategy that returns market-beating results. It must then decide how to use those results to attract new investors.

Weaknesses

Weaknesses stop an organization from performing at its optimum level. They are areas where the business needs to improve to remain competitive: a weak brand, higher-than-average turnover, high levels of debt, an inadequate supply chain, or lack of capital.

Opportunities

Opportunities refer to favorable external factors that could give an organization a competitive advantage. For example, if a country cuts tariffs, a car manufacturer can export its cars into a new market, increasing sales and market share.

Threats

Threats refer to factors that have the potential to harm an organization. For example, a drought is a threat to a wheat-producing company, as it may destroy or reduce the crop yield. Other common threats include things like rising costs for materials, increasing competition, tight labor supply, and so on.¹⁵²

Table-1

SWOT analysis of RoboClean vacuum cleaner by AURA company

Strengths	Opportunities
1. Availability of satisfied customers in 35	1. A high level of opportunity to use new

¹⁵¹ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/swot.asp>

¹⁵² <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/swot.asp>

<p>countries</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Excellent organization of service and support 3. Popularity of the company's mission to be recognized as "Efficient, quiet and the perfect user's friend" 4. Diversity of the company's products and functions 5. The company's strong brand and team of qualified specialists 	<p>marketing tools to increase the number of customers and buyers</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Existence of opportunities to effectively use product pricing strategies based on customers' purchasing abilities 3. Availability of new market opportunities in the countries of Central Asia and Southeast Asia
<p>Weaknesses</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use of a high, authoritative price policy when setting prices for products 2. The presence of small defects and malfunctions in certain types of products 	<p>Threats</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Availability of low-priced goods market for customers with low purchasing power 2. Political and economic processes in the neighboring countries cause problems in attracting new markets

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